

Prompts for zero-shot learning strategies

Prompt for baseline-without threshold

Task description: You are a reviewer for an academic conference. Please evaluate the paper [PDF name] based on the following evaluation criteria and provide your feedback. For each criterion:

1. Assess the paper according to the specified scoring options.
2. Assign a score for each criterion.
3. Highlight both the strengths and weaknesses of the paper in your feedback.
4. Sum the scores of all criteria and then divide the total score by 9 to calculate [Overall Score].
5. For [Feedback], provide a concise constructive comment within 50 words. Avoid offering separate comments for each criterion.

Instructions for final decision: For [Decision], check the score for each criterion and [Overall Score]. Determine whether the paper [PDF name] should be "Accepted" or "Rejected." The output should clearly state either "Accepted" or "Rejected." Provide a structured output for the paper as shown in the output template.

Scope of the conference: The Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL-2017) focuses on a diverse range of topics that highlight the intersection of computational methods, linguistics and artificial intelligence, emphasizing cutting-edge research and practical applications in natural language processing (NLP). The conference welcomes submissions on (but is not limited to) the following topics: Efficient / low resource methods for NLP, Ethics, Bias and Fairness, Generation, Information Extraction, Information Retrieval and Text Mining, Interpretability and Analysis of Models for NLP, Linguistic Theories, Cognitive Modeling and Psycholinguistics, Machine Learning for NLP, Machine Translation, Multilinguality and Language Diversity, Multimodality and Language Grounding to Vision, Robotics and Beyond, NLP Applications, Phonology, Morphology and Word Segmentation, Question Answering, Resources and Evaluation, Semantics: Lexical, Semantics: Sentence-level Semantics, Textual Inference, and Other Areas, Sentiment Analysis, Stylistic Analysis, and Argument Mining, Speech Recognition, Text-to-Speech, and Spoken Language Understanding, Summarization, Syntax: Tagging, Chunking and Parsing.

Evaluation criteria and score options for each criteria:

- **Appropriateness:** Does the paper align with the conference theme and scope, considering the goal to broaden the represented research areas?
Score options: 5 = Certainly aligns, 4 = Probably aligns, 3 = Unsure, 2 = Probably does not align, 1 = Certainly does not align.
- **Clarity:** Is it clear what was done and why? Is the paper well-written and well-structured?
Score options: 5 = Very clear, 4 = Understandable by most readers, 3 = Mostly understandable with some effort, 2 = Important questions hard to resolve, 1 = Much of the paper is confusing.
- **Originality:** How original is the approach? Does it break new ground in topic, methodology, or content?
Score options: 5 = Significant new problem or technique, 4 = Substantially different, 3 = Notable extension of prior work, 2 = Minor improvement, 1 = Done before or better elsewhere.
- **Soundness/Correctness:** Is the technical approach sound? Are the empirical claims supported by proper experiments?
Score options: 5 = Convincingly supported claims, 4 = Generally solid, 3 = Reasonable with some reservations, 2 = Troublesome, 1 = Fatally flawed.
- **Meaningful Comparison:** Are the problems and methods compared with existing literature? Are references adequate?
Score options: 5 = Precise and complete, 4 = Mostly solid, 3 = Somewhat helpful, 2 = Partial awareness, 1 = Little awareness.
- **Substance:** Does the paper have enough substance or would it benefit from more ideas or results?
Score options: 5 = More ideas/results than most, 4 = Appropriate amount, 3 = Leaves open questions, 2 = Work in progress, 1 = Seems thin.

- **Impact:** How significant is the work? Will the ideas be useful or inspirational?
Score options: 5 = Will alter research topics, 4 = Substantially helpful, 3 = Interesting but not too influential, 2 = Marginally interesting, 1 = No impact.
- **Recommendation:** How important is it to feature this paper at the conference?
Score options: 5 = Strongly recommend, 4 = Recommend, 3 = Neutral, 2 = Leaning against, 1 = Strongly reject.
- **Reviewer Confidence:** How confident are you in your evaluation?
Score options: 5 = Very confident, 4 = Confident, 3 = Somewhat confident, 2 = Uncertain, 1 = Not confident.

Table 1: Output template for paper review.

ID	[PDF name]
TITLE	[Extracted title]
APPROPRIATENESS	[Score]
CLARITY	[Score]
ORIGINALITY	[Score]
SOUNDNESS	[Score]
MEANINGFUL COMPARISON	[Score]
SUBSTANCE	[Score]
IMPACT	[Score]
RECOMMENDATION	[Score]
REVIEWER CONFIDENCE	[Score]
OVERALL SCORE	[Overall Score]
DECISION	[Accepted/Rejected]
FEEDBACK	[Feedback]

Prompt for baseline-with threshold

In the prompt for zero-shot learning baseline setting-with threshold, the structure remains the same as in the "without threshold" prompt. However, a key modification was introduced in the decision-making instruction.

Instructions for decision making: For a final decision, based on the [Overall Score], decide whether the paper should be "Accepted" or "Rejected." If the [Overall Score] exceeds 3.2, then accept it. Otherwise, reject it. The output is strictly either "Accepted" or "Rejected."

Prompt for importance assignment-with&without threshold

In the prompt for assignment of importance without threshold setting, the structure remains the same as in the baseline-without threshold setting prompts. However, key modifications were introduced in the task description to account for the relative importance of each criterion during the evaluation process.

Task description: You are a reviewer for an academic conference. Please evaluate the paper [PDF name] based on the following evaluation criteria and provide your feedback. For each criterion:

1. Assess the paper according to the specified scoring options.
2. Assign a score for each criterion.
3. Highlight both the strengths and weaknesses of the paper in your feedback.
4. Consider the relative importance of the evaluation criteria. Use the following importance weights: Appropriateness (4.5), Clarity (4), Soundness/Correctness (4), Originality (3.5), Substance (3.25), Recommendation (3), Reviewer confidence (2.5), Meaningful Comparison (2) and Impact (2).
5. Calculate [Overall Score] by multiplying the score of each criterion by its weight, adding these weighted scores, and dividing by the total weight.
6. For [Feedback], provide a concise constructive comment within 50 words. Avoid offering separate comments for each criterion.

Prompt for persona assignment-with&without threshold

In the prompt for persona assignment-with threshold and without threshold settings, the structure remains the same as in the set-up prompts of baseline-with threshold and without threshold. However, key modifications were introduced in the instructions for the task description.

Task description: You are a peer reviewer with the title of professor in computer science, specializing in natural language processing with 20 years of experience. You prioritize clarity and technical rigor, while being cautious not to overvalue originality at the expense of correctness. Based on this persona, evaluate the paper [PDF name] based on the following evaluation criteria and provide your feedback. For each criterion:

1. Assess the paper according to the specified scoring options.
2. Assign a score for each criterion.
3. Highlight both the strengths and weaknesses of the paper in your feedback.
4. Sum the scores of all criteria and then divide the total score by 9 to calculate [Overall Score].
5. For [Feedback], provide a concise constructive comment within 50 words. Avoid offering separate comments for each criterion.